

SYSTEM $[\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3\text{—H}_2\text{O}]$ IN RELATION TO THE DEHYDRATING PROPERTIES OF ALUMINA

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The isobars of alumina, prepared from different sources have been obtained and their mechanism of water holding has been discussed in relation to their different catalytic activity. The catalytic activity is dependent on the capacity of alumina to hold water in 'colitic condition'. Tendency to form hydrates is shown alumina, which is known to be a poor catalyst.

Adkins and his co-workers (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1922, **44**, 385, 2175 ; 1923, **45**, 809 ; 1924, **46**, 130, 2291 ; 1925, **47**, 807) found that alumina prepared in different ways exhibited varying catalytic activity towards the decomposition of formic acid, alcohols, and esters. This could be hardly ascribed to the different surface areas of the several preparations, as the variation was not confined to the total speed of the reaction but also affected the relative speeds of two alternate modes of decomposition which these substances undergo e.g., (i) dehydration and (ii) dehydrogenation in the case of alcohols and formic acid. They stress on the difference in the spacing of the aluminium atoms rather than the ability of alumina to absorb water during dehydration, as a plausible explanation for the difference in activity. X-ray and electron diffraction studies on aluminium hydroxide and alumina (*vide infra*) do not confirm the difference in spacing of the aluminium atom in the various preparations. Further, the experimental results of Adkins and Nissen (*loc.cit.*) on the formation of nitriles from amides stand in sharp contrast to their own suggestion. However, a study of alumina-water system might afford a clue to the nature of alumina as a dehydration catalyst, since according to Dover and Marden (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1917, **39**, 1609) the loss of water on heating $\text{Al}(\text{OH})_3$ up to 500° is quantitatively reabsorbed if the ignited sample is kept in moist air for 24 hours.

Weiser and Milligan (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1934, **38**, 1175 ; 1940, **44**, 1081) from X-ray and electron diffraction studies conclude that all precipitated varieties of hydrous oxides of alumina are as $[\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ which transform through the unstable $[\alpha\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ to the stable $(\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O})$. Starting from different materials they find that the same structure is obtained though the size of the primary crystals may vary as in the case of aluminium hydroxide from sulphate.

Fricke and Severin (*Z. anorg. Chem.*, 1932, **205**, 287) report X-ray evidence for $[\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ in the sample of aluminium hydroxide by precipitation by CO_2 on sodium aluminate. Weiser and Milligan (*loc.cit.*) report that $[\alpha\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ changes into $[\gamma\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ at 205° , though stable up to 145° . The hydroxide from sodium aluminate is stable up to 160° and decomposes by losing water thereafter at a slow and steady rate.

Mead (cf. Milligan) finds that while the hydroxide shows X-ray evidence for $[\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 3\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ but on igniting to 325° there is no trihydrate but only evidence of crystalline $[\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O}]$ and corundum structure of Al_2O_3 and that absorption of water does not alter the structure. Isobaric studies of Milligan (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1922, **26**, 247) give no support for a monohydrate, while Rooksby (*Trans. Ceram. Soc.*, 1929, **28**, 399) reports a monohydrate, and Edward and Tosterud (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1933, **37**, 433) give evidence of a second monohydrate.

From the above, the nature of hydroxide formed is not definite except in certain main details and does not help us far in the problem of Adkin's catalysts. It is proposed in this paper to study in detail the isobars of aluminium hydroxide prepared by different methods with a view to elucidating the mechanism of their water holding, since according to Bancroft (*J. Phys. Chem.*, 1917, **21**, 602) a catalyst tends to produce that system which it absorbs most strongly.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Aluminium Hydroxide

(a) *From the Nitrate.*—Aluminium nitrate crystals (50 g. of C.P., Rideal de Haehn) was dissolved in 350 c.c. of distilled water and the solution was boiled for a few minutes. To this solution was added ammonia (sp. gr. 0.91) dropwise with stirring till the precipitation was complete. The precipitate was boiled with a large excess of water and kept boiling for 15 minutes. It was filtered and the precipitate washed till free from nitrate and ammonia. The precipitate was dried at 100° in an oven for 5 hours and ground to fine powder in an agate mortar, sieved to 100 mesh and kept in a vacuum desiccator over silica gel drier.

(b) *From Ammonium Alum.*—Ammonium alum (B.D.H. Analar, 112.5 g.) was dissolved in 500 c. c. of distilled water and the solution boiled. Ammonia (sp. gr. 0.91) was added dropwise with stirring till complete precipitation. The hydroxide was boiled with a large quantity of water for 15 minutes, filtered and washed free from ammonium sulphate. The precipitate was dried at 95° for 5 hours. The sample was ground in an agate mortar, sieved to 100 mesh and stored as above in a desiccator.

(c) *From Aluminium Acetate.*—Pure aluminium acetate (Johnson, 20 g.) was taken in 500 c.c. of distilled water and hydrolysed under repeated boiling. The insoluble basic salt was filtered, washed free from acetic acid, and the precipitate was treated with a few c. c. of ammonium hydroxide and boiled with additional water. This was repeated twice over and the complete hydrolysis was over in 3 days. The sample was thoroughly washed till free from acetic acid and ammonia, dried at 90° for 8 hours, ground, sieved to 100 mesh and stored as above.

(d) *Le Chatelier Method.*—The aluminium hydroxide from (b) above, was dissolved in sodium hydroxide (6*N*) and filtered. The solution was maintained between 60° and 70° and a slow and steady stream of CO₂ was passed into it. The precipitated alumina was filtered, washed free from traces of caustic soda and carbonate, dried at 100° and sieved to 100 mesh. The sample was kept in the desiccator as above.

Isobars of Aluminium Hydroxide Samples.—Alumina (1 to 2 g.) was weighed accurately and kept in a calibrated electric furnace, temperatures of which were maintained at different values from 100° to 400° in steps of 10°. The temperature in each case was kept constant within $\pm 2^\circ$. The samples were kept at each temperature for 3 hours and more and weighed to constant weight after cooling in a desiccator. Final heating at 400° dehydrated the samples completely. Several experiments were conducted with each

type of alumina described above and concordant results obtained. On the initial and the final weights of the samples, the number of moles of water held by per mole of alumina was calculated. The graphs in Fig. 1 give the representative value for the isobars of alumina prepared from different starting materials and by different methods. The initial water contents were below 3 moles of water per mole of alumina since observations were made only on samples heated to 100° below which some quantity of water might have been lost.

FIG. 1

DISCUSSION

It is seen from the results presented in Fig. 1 that the nature of the Le Chatelier's alumina is entirely different from those of the others obtained by precipitation from the different salts of aluminium. The latter give similar isobars and form a class by themselves. The curves (A, B & C) for the system, $[\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3-\text{H}_2\text{O}]$ is bivariant and give continuous desorption curves. The curves for hydrates according to phase rule are univariant giving stepped curves denoting a definite hydrate at each step. There appears to be no definite monohydrate in these cases and the stoichiometric formulae describe only a limiting composition. Water is removed by dehydration in a continuous manner without giving rise to a new solid phase. Emeleus and Anderson ("Modern Aspects of Inorganic Chemistry", 1942, p. 163) consider from similar cases that water is neither bound by covalent bonds nor hydrogen bonds as in the case of regular hydrates but as being packed between the layers of the crystal or in the interstices of the structure. Water held in such a manner is classified by them as 'zeolite water.' The removal of zeolite water according to them

may change the spacing between the successive layers of the crystal. The curve (G,F,E,D) for the same system is made up of two bivariant systems (GF & ED), one with a limiting composition of 3 moles of water and the other of 1 mole of water. Thus, the sudden transition (FE) at 220° denotes a change from one bivariant system to another. This part of the curve is similar to that which would be obtained in a univariant system [$\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$, $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_3 \cdot \text{H}_2\text{O} - \text{H}_2\text{O}$ vapour]. In this case water above 1 mole according to Emelius and Anderson (*loc. cit.*) would be what is described as "lattice water", which is a border case between chemically bound water and "zeolite water".

From Adkin's work (*loc. cit.*) it is seen that precipitated alumina from aluminium salts is about 1.5 times more active than that prepared by Le Chatelier method for dehydration. So it could be concluded that capacity of alumina to hold water in zeolitic condition gives a more active variety of catalyst for dehydration reactions than either lattice type or chemically bound type of water holding: Removal of zeolitic water, altering the spacing of the successive layers of the crystal, might help to render the catalyst more active. Evidence for this view is forthcoming in the recent work of Bentley and Faecchim (*J. Soc. Chem. Ind.*, 1945, **64**, 148) who rendered a relatively less active alumina into an active dehydration catalyst by alternate hydration and dehydration. Thus the difference in the activity of alumina catalyst in dehydration processes would appear to be due to the difference in the mode of water of holding and not to the spacing of the aluminium atoms.

It is well known that fineness of subdivision increases the catalytic activity. In the case of alumina, such subdivision might increase the area of the effective surface or might alter the mechanism of water holding. Experiments of Hagiwara (J. Alexander, "Colloid Chemistry", 1926, Vol. I, pp. 647-658) on the isobars of aluminium hydroxide show that fine grinding changes the curve from univariant one to a bivariant one. In other words, fine particles take up water in a zeolitic manner, while bigger crystals form definite hydrates.

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